

SENTIMENTAL BUSINESS CYCLES
ONLINE APPENDIX
NOT INTENDED FOR PUBLICATION

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Abstract

This Online Appendix presents the data description and additional empirical analysis such as robustness checks that we have left out of the main draft of the paper for economy of space.

1 Data description

Variables in the VAR

Our baseline VAR consists of seven variables: log consumer confidence, the unemployment rate, log industrial production, log CPI prices, the federal funds rate, log macroeconomic uncertainty and log real stock market prices. The data are monthly spanning January 1965 to August 2007 in the baseline, and extended up to November 2018 in robustness checks. We detrend all macroeconomic variables (except for the federal funds rate) by fourth-order time polynomials. We include 18 lags.

Data on consumer confidence are obtained from the University of Michigan Survey of Consumers. More precisely, we use the index of consumer expectations (ICE), which is computed as the relative favorability score on three broad questions: expected financial well-being, expected business conditions (BUS12), and expected broad economic conditions (BUS5). For robustness, we also consider alternative confidence indices including the overall index of consumer sentiment (ICS), as well as the index of current economic conditions (ICC) and two components of ICE, namely BUS12 and BUS5. Opinions compared to a “normal” state are collected and the difference between positive and negative answers provides a qualitative index on economic conditions.

Data for the remaining macroeconomic variables are retrieved from the Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED), made available online by the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. Data for the unemployment rate (UR) and consumer price index (CPI) for all urban consumers are both produced by the Bureau of Labor Statistics. Data for the industrial production index (IP) and the effective federal funds rate (FFR) are produced by the Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System. The series on macroeconomic uncertainty is constructed by Jurado *et al.* (2015). Stock market prices are deflated using the CPI index and also come from the FRED database.

In the robustness analysis we augment the VAR with additional variables: consumption of durables and non-durables, vacancy postings, labor market tightness, the VIX uncertainty index, economic policy uncertainty (EPU), and total factor productivity (TFP). The data on consumption of durables and non durables as well as the VIX index of S&P 500 stock price options volatility are also obtained from the FRED. Data on vacancy postings, based on the Conference Board’s ‘Help Wanted’ index, were obtained from Stock and Watson (2012) replication files for the paper “Disentangling the Channels of the 2007-2009 Recession”. The economic policy uncertainty index is constructed by Baker *et al.* (2016). For TFP we use the utilization-adjusted TFP series estimated by Fernald and Wang (2016). These series are all expressed in logs. Moreover, all the data we use in our analysis are seasonally adjusted, except for shootings and the federal funds rate. Those that were not already seasonally-adjusted by the data source provider, we seasonally adjust using the Census Bureau’s X13 tool, namely all confidence indices (ICE, ICS, ICC, BUS5, BUS12), asset price and uncertainty measures (S&P 500 Stock Price Index, Jurado *et al.* (2015)’s

uncertainty index, the VIX, EPU), vacancy postings and utilization-adjusted TFP.

Mass shootings

We assemble a comprehensive dataset of mass shootings spanning the sample period January 1965 until November 2018, drawing upon existing databases compiled by MotherJones (2020), Duwe (2007)¹, and The-Violence-Project (2019). We supplement these with information obtained from Wikipedia (2020) as well as news reports and court reports.

The MotherJones (2020) database documents public mass shootings since 1982 in which the motive appeared to be indiscriminate killing, satisfying the following criteria:

- (i) the incident was associated with minimum *four* fatalities (excluding the perpetrator) in a single geographical location;²
- (ii) The killings were carried out by a lone shooter;³
- (iii) The shootings occurred in a public place. Crimes primarily related to gang activity, armed robbery, criminal competition, insurance fraud, arguments, romantic triangle, or other commonplace circumstances are not included, nor are mass killings that took place in private homes (often stemming from domestic violence).

We adopt the above criteria in our search for additional events in the period prior to 1982, and for cross-checking events in the common sample period.

The datasets by Duwe (2007) and The-Violence-Project (2019), which span a longer period back in time, rely on very similar - but not completely identical - definitions of mass shootings. Duwe (2007) defines these as “incidents that occur in the absence of other criminal activity (e.g., robberies, drug deals, gang “turf wars,” et cetera) in which a gun was used to kill four or more victims at a public location within a 24-hour period”. The Violence Project, a non-profit, non-partisan research center dedicated to reducing violence in society, follows the Congressional Research Service definition for mass shootings, as “a multiple homicide incident in which four or more victims are murdered with firearms—not including the offender(s)—within one event, and at least some of the murders occurred in a public location or locations in close geographical proximity (e.g., a workplace, school, restaurant, or other public settings), and the murders are not attributable to any other underlying criminal activity or commonplace circumstance.”

¹Grant Duwe has supplied us with an updated dataset that covers the sample period 1902 to 2016.

²The MotherJones database also includes a handful of cases known as “spree killings” in which the killings occurred in more than one location in a short period of time; otherwise the incidents occurred in a single place only. We follow MotherJones in including these. Furthermore, MotherJones includes shootings with three fatalities from 2013 onwards. We use minimum four fatalities throughout the sample for consistency.

³We include along with MotherJones (2020) the Columbine massacre and the Westside middle school killings both of which have two perpetrators.

In creating our mass shootings database, we have checked all three datasets for consistency using electronically available news reports and court reports. During this process we found several errors in the number of fatalities and victims reported by MotherJones that we have corrected. Our final database, spanning 1965-2018, contains 154 shootings with 4 or more fatalities (plotted in Figure 1), of which 42 incidents resulted in 7 or more fatalities and 20 incidents resulted in 10 or more fatalities, with 6 episodes concentrated in the last two calendar years alone. Table 1 lists the most serious incidents.

Figure 1: **Timeline of Mass Shootings, 1965-2018m11**

Note: The graph presents the timeline of fatalities in mass shootings with 4 or more fatalities over the period 1965:1-2018:11.

As far as our baseline instrument is concerned – which considers large mass shooting incidents with seven or more fatalities – the two databases that we use for the period prior to 1982 (when MotherJones (2020) starts) agree apart from one incident: Duwe (2007) includes the Bonners shooting in Los Angeles, California on April 22, 1973, which had seven fatalities, while The-Violence-Project (2019) does not. We have included it in our analysis but the results are robust to excluding it. In the common sample period post-1982, the three datasets coincide in reporting the same mass shooting events with seven or more fatalities except for: a) a shooting with eight fatalities in Alaska in November 1982 (reported only in Duwe (2007)), which we have excluded from our sample as we were unable to confirm any information about the incident; b) the mass murder where six villagers disappeared in Manley Hot Springs in 1984 and were thought to have been killed by Michael Silka (reported in Duwe (2007) and The-Violence-Project (2019) but not MotherJones (2020)), which we exclude since the circumstances surrounding this incident were unclear; c) a mass murder in December 1988 where David Burke crashed a plane killing 42 people (reported only in Duwe (2007)), which we exclude since it was not a mass shooting; and d) the Copley Township shooting in August 2011 where Michael Hance went on a shooting spree

Table 1: Mass Shootings With 10 or More Fatalities

Incident	Location	Date	Fatalities	Injuries
University of Texas Tower shooting	Austin, Texas	August 1966	16	30
San Ysidro’s McDonalds massacre	San Ysidro, California	July 1984	21	19
U.S. Postal Service shooting	Edmond, Oklahoma	August 1986	14	6
Luby’s massacre	Killeen, Texas	October 1991	23	20
Columbine High School massacre	Littleton, Colorado	April 1999	13	21
Atlanta day trading spree killing	Atlanta, Georgia	July 1999	12	13
Virginia Tech massacre	Blacksburg, Virginia	April 2007	32	17
Binghamton shootings	Binghamton, New York	April 2009	13	4
Fort Hood massacre	Fort Hood, Texas	November 2009	13	32
Aurora Theatre shooting	Aurora, Colorado	July 2012	12	58
Newtown School shooting	Newtown, Connecticut	December 2012	27	2
Washington Navy Yard shooting	Washington, D.C.	September 2013	12	3
San Bernadino mass shooting	San Bernadino, California	December 2015	14	22
Orland Nightclub massacre	Orlando, Florida	June 2016	49	53
Las Vegas Strip Massacre	Las Vegas, Nevada	October 2017	58	411
Texas First Baptist Church massacre	Sutherland Springs, Texas	November 2017	26	20
Marjory Stoneman Douglas High School	Parkland, Florida	February 2018	17	17
Santa Fe High school shooting	Santa Fe, Texas	May 2018	10	13
Tree of Life Synagogue Shooting	Pittsburg, Pennsylvania	October 2018	11	6
Thousand Oaks Night Club shooting	Thousand Oaks, California	November 2018	12	16

targeting his girlfriend and her family and neighbors, shooting seven people dead (reported only in The-Violence-Project (2019)), which we have included in our sample.

When it comes to mass shootings with less than seven fatalities, there are more differences across the datasets. One source of discrepancies relates to the definition of the number of fatalities: MotherJones (2020) includes incidents with three fatalities or more (offender excluded) starting in 2013, and four fatalities or more before 2013, while the other two sources put the lower limit at four fatalities consistently throughout. For consistency, we only consider shootings with four or more fatalities throughout our sample period. In addition, Duwe (2007) and The-Violence-Project (2019) include some incidents that upon further checks turn out to meet the criteria for mass shootings⁴. We have included these incidents in our dataset. However, some incidents reported in the three databases were not indiscriminate shootings in a public space and were related to personal disputes. Those events listed in Table 2 are excluded from our dataset. The first column presents the incident number in The-Violence-Project (2019), while the second and third columns indicate whether the event appears also in the Duwe (2007) and MotherJones (2020) databases with an index of 1 or 0, and the fourth column reports the reason why we have excluded these events. In the sensitivity analysis we further exclude incidents from Duwe (2007) and The-Violence-Project (2019) that are borderline cases of personal disputes, listed in Table 3.

⁴Duwe (2007) argues that the MotherJones (2020) database significantly under-reports incidents that meet its definitional requirements, missing more than 40% of the cases between 1982 and 2013.

Table 2: Excluded Mass Shootings

Violence	Duwe	MotherJones	Description	Location	Date	Fat.	Inj.
-	1	0	Criminal activity	Albany, NY	Apr 1970	4	0
-	1	0	Airplane, not mass shooting	Gonzalez, TX	Jun 1972	4	0
-	1	0	Multiple perpetrators	Sioux Falls, SD	Nov 1973	4	0
-	1	0	Unclear motive, maybe mafia	Holmes Beach, FL	Aug 1980	4	1
-	1	0	Personal dispute, only 3 shot (2 died of smoke)	Pembroke Pines, FL	Mar 1981	5	0
-	1	0	Personal dispute	Elyria, OH	Jan 1982	4	0
-	1	0	Criminal activity	Stoddard, MO	Jul 1982	4	0
-	1	0	Unsolved	Unreported, AL	Nov 1982	8	0
24	0	0	Personal dispute	New York, NY	Feb 1983	4	1
27	1	0	Circumstances unclear	Manley Hot Springs, AK	May 1984	8	1
-	1	0	Personal dispute	Cassia, ID	Sep 1984	4	1
-	1	0	Personal dispute	Boston, MA	Aug 1987	5	2
-	1	0	Mass murder - no shooting	San Luis Obispo, CA	Dec 1988	42	0
-	1	0	Mass murder - no shooting	Storey, NV	Apr 1991	4	0
43	1	0	Personal dispute	Harrodsburg, KY	Nov 1991	4	0
-	1	0	Personal dispute	Moniteau, MO	Dec 1991	4	1
45	1	0	Robbery - Revenge	Phoenix, AZ	Mar 1992	4	0
48	1	0	Personal dispute	Paso Robles, CA	Nov 1992	6	1
64	0	0	Personal dispute	Bartow, FL	Dec 1997	4	0
93	1	0	Not public space	Atlanta, GA	Mar 2005	3	2
112	0	0	Personal dispute	Mt. Airy, NC	Sep 2009	4	0
-	1	0	Personal dispute	Grand Prairie, TX	Jul 2011	5	3
-	1	1	Personal dispute	Norcross, Georgia	Feb 2012	4	0
131	0	1	Personal dispute	Federal Way, Washington	Apr 2013	5	0
135	1	1	Personal dispute	Alturas, California	Feb 2014	4	2
145-146	0	0	Multiple shooters	Wilkesburg, PA	Mar 2016	5	3

2 Individual level regressions

To study how mass shootings affect local confidence, we map mass shootings to the counties in which they occurred (shown in Figure 2 in the main text). We use minimum four fatalities as a cut-off. Between January 2000 to June 2017 there were 71 mass shootings which occurred in 62 different counties, providing substantial cross-sectional variation. Figure 2 plots a histogram of mass shooting fatalities and victims during the sample period.

Pappa *et al.* (2019) have already provided evidence that mass shootings are exogenous to county-level conditions. We present further evidence suggesting that the occurrence of mass shootings is exogenous, i.e. not caused by local economic conditions. First, examining the cross-sectional distribution of shootings across counties, simple t-tests for differences in means do not reject that counties that experience mass shootings have equal confidence levels and unemployment rates as those that do not (Table 4). Second, exploiting the panel dimension of our data, we estimate a linear probability model and find no impact of lagged unemployment

Table 3: Mass shootings in our sample with borderline personal dispute motives

Violence Project ID	Duwe incidence	Location	Date	Fat.	Inj.
25	1	McCarthy, AK	Mar 1983	6	2
26	1	College Station, TX	Oct 1983	6	0
30	1	Hot Springs, AR	July 1984	5	1
31	1	Connellsville, PA	Mar 1985	4	2
40	1	Ridgewood, NJ	Oct 1991	4	0
-	1	Jackson, MS	Jul 1993	5	0
58	1	Los Angeles, CA	Jul 1995	4	0
61	1	West St Jackson, MS	Apr 1996	5	3
62	1	Colebrook, NH	Aug 1997	4	4
70	1	Gonzalez, LA	Mar 1999	4	4
78	1	Irving, TX	Mar 2000	5	1
81	0	Houston, TX	Jan 2001	4	0
84	1	Sacramento, CA	Sep 2001	5	2
85	1	South Bend, IN	Mar 2002	4	5
88	1	Chicago, IL	Aug 2003	6	0
89	1	Oldtown, ID	Oct 2003	4	0
90	1	Kansas City, KS	Jul 2004	6	2
91	1	Sawyer, WI	Nov 2004	6	2
96	1	Honey Grove, TX	Aug 2005	4	0
99	1	Baton Rouge, LA	May 2006	5	1
107	1	Santa Maria, CA	Mar 2008	4	0
-	1	Syracuse, NY	Feb 2009	4	0
115	1	N. Hollywood, CA	Apr 2010	4	2
116	1	Hialeah, FL	Jun 2010	4	3
119	0	Jackson, KY	Sep 2010	5	0
121	0	Copley, OH	Aug 2011	7	1
141	0	Yazzo City, MS	Nov 2015	6	0
151	0	Yazzo City, MS	Feb 2017	4	0
152	0	Rothschild, WI	Mar 2017	4	0
159	0	Detroit, MI	Feb 2018	4	0

rates on the probability of mass shootings occurring in a given county (see Table 2 in the main text). Taken all together, we find no evidence that the distribution of mass shootings across counties and time is related to underlying economic conditions.

Table 4: Cross-Sectional Exogeneity of Mass Shootings: T-test for Difference in Means

Mean value for:	Counties without	Counties with	T-statistic
	Shootings	Shootings	
Confidence	2.74	2.89	-1.08
Δ Confidence	0.02	0.12	-0.68
Unemployment rate	6.29	6.32	-0.09
Δ Unemployment rate x 100	0.13	0.05	0.92

Figure 2: Histogram of Mass Shooting Fatalities and Victims during 2000-2017

We then estimate how mass shootings affect sentiments for residents in the county of the shooting by regressing the six-month change in individual consumer confidence ($C_{i,j,t}$) on county-level mass shooting fatalities ($S_{j,t}$) cumulated over those six months. These results are presented in Table 3 in the main text. Here, we also present results for additional sensitivity tests in Table 5. Results are robust to clustering standard errors at narrower as well as wider geographical areas, e.g. at the county level (column 1) and state level (column 2). Results are also robust to excluding mass shootings that can be linked to personal motives (column 3) and to considering the raw data in Mother Jones' publicly-available website (column 4).

Table 5: Robustness Tests

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Δ Confidence	Δ Confidence	Δ Confidence	Δ Confidence
Total fatalities	-0.016** (0.008)	-0.016** (0.008)		
Total fatalities (excl. personal motives)			-0.015** (0.007)	
Total fatalities (Mother Jones data)				-0.016*** (0.006)
Δ Personal finances	0.063*** (0.006)	0.063*** (0.004)	0.063*** (0.005)	0.063*** (0.005)
Δ County unemployment	-0.009 (0.010)	-0.009 (0.011)	-0.009 (0.010)	-0.009 (0.010)
Constant	0.151 (0.132)	0.151 (0.119)	0.151 (0.137)	0.151 (0.137)
Observations	36,264	36,264	36,264	36,264
R-squared	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.027
Time FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
SE cluster	County	State	MSA	MSA
F-statistic	4.2	4.1	4.2	6.8

Robust standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Finally, we also present results for the ICE measure of confidence, which is used throughout our aggregate-level analysis, in Table 6. Although the number of observations drops significantly, results are still robust to using dummy variables for shootings with a large number of fatalities

as well as victims (columns 3 and 5). These measures of mass shootings are the most robust to large outliers.

Table 6: ICE Confidence

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Δ ICE				
Total fatalities	-0.211 (0.177)				
Total fatalities (min. 7)		-0.257 (0.222)			
Dummy for min. 10 fatalities			-11.628* (6.104)		
Total victims				-0.075 (0.074)	
Dummy for min. 10 victims					-9.115*** (3.344)
Δ Personal finances	1.880*** (0.133)	1.880*** (0.133)	1.880*** (0.133)	1.880*** (0.133)	1.880*** (0.133)
County unemployment	-0.294 (0.372)	-0.295 (0.372)	-0.296 (0.372)	-0.294 (0.372)	-0.297 (0.372)
Constant	-3.442 (3.074)	-3.453 (3.080)	-3.453 (3.080)	-3.448 (3.078)	-3.453 (3.080)
Observations	39,203	39,203	39,203	39,203	39,203
R-squared	0.053	0.053	0.053	0.053	0.053
Time FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SE cluster	MSA	MSA	MSA	MSA	MSA
F-statistic	1.42	1.34	3.63	1.01	7.43

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

3 Robustness checks

In this section, we investigate the robustness of our baseline results to the sample period, the instrument used, alternative measures of confidence and mass fatalities, and detrending the data.

3.A Alternative sample periods

Our benchmark excludes the Great Recession. We now show results when we extend the sample in time. In Figure 3 we extend the sample to November 2018. Now the F -statistics indicate that the instrument is weak and the confidence bands become wider. However, excluding the Las Vegas shooting in October 2017, by far the biggest mass shooting in the US history, from the longer sample reconfirms our previous findings, see Figure 4.

In the baseline specification presented in the main text we linearly interpolate consumer confidence prior to 1977. As one might be concerned that this adds error to our results, we

Figure 3: **Baseline Specification: Full Time Sample, 1965m1-2018m11**

present impulse responses for the sub-sample period spanning 1977:1-2007:8, showing that results are robust to controlling for errors due to interpolation (see Figure 5). Moreover, the F -statistics remain high at 9.1 and 27.0 considering this sample period.

Figure 4: **Baseline Specification: Sample 1965m1-2018m11, excluding Las Vegas**

Finally, we also investigate the robustness of our results when considering an earlier sample period, spanning 1965:1 until 1995:6. Figure 6 shows that, while responses of real variables such as industrial production and unemployment rate as well as uncertainty are robust, other

Figure 5: **Baseline Specification: Sample 1977m1-2007m8**

variables show a somewhat stronger response in this earlier sample period. For example, the federal funds rate falls, consistent with the lower path for consumer price inflation (leaning against the wind). Moreover, stock market prices fall significantly on impact. To eliminate any suspicion that the sentiment shocks are confounding stock price news shocks (about future TFP) for this earlier sample period, we note that when augmenting our VAR with TFP (whether adjusted by utilization or not), we see no evidence of TFP falling throughout the projection horizon.

3.B Alternative Instruments

Our benchmark instrumental variable is fatalities in mass shootings, where we consider incidents with seven or more fatalities. This relatively high threshold ensures that the shooting events considered are robust across different dataset and that they receive enough media coverage to impact on consumer sentiments at the aggregate US level. In this section we consider robustness of our results to alternative versions of this instrument.

When we use a broader definition of mass shootings that includes incidents with four or more fatalities, the dynamic response to sentiment shocks remains broadly robust while the instrument weakens. The wider confidence bands perhaps reflect more noise and less media coverage of these less lethal events (see Figure 7). Results are unchanged when we exclude small shootings with 4 to 6 fatalities that could be considered borderline cases related to personal disputes as listed in Table 3 (results not presented here for economy of space).

Impulse responses remain highly robust to considering mass shootings victims as the instru-

Figure 6: **Baseline Specification: Sample 1965m1-1995m6**

Figure 7: **Alternative IV - Minimum 4 Fatalities in Mass Shootings**

ment, measured as the number of injuries in addition to fatalities, still considering only mass shootings with at least 7 fatalities (see Figure 8). The instrument weakens and confidence bands widen when we consider the number of victims also for smaller shootings with fewer than 4 fatalities (results not presented here for economy of space).

In the main paper, we show evidence that results are robust to shootings outliers, using indicator variables for the mass shooting events instead of measuring their intensity (fatalities) as a proxy in the VAR. Instrument strength remains strong when we consider dummies for larger

Figure 8: **Alternative IV - Mass Shooting Victims**

shootings with at least seven fatalities, (see Figure 7 in the main paper). Instead, the instrument becomes substantially weaker when we use indicator variables for mass shooting events that also include the smaller shootings, with minimum four fatalities, although the IRFs remain robust even in this case (results not presented here for economy of space).

One might be concerned about a seasonal pattern in mass shootings, which is not captured in our baseline specification, where the mass shooting fatalities instrument is not seasonally adjusted. However, we do not find seasonality in this series. In any case, results are robust when we include monthly dummies as exogenous variables in our baseline VAR (Figure 9). Results are also robust when we seasonally adjust the mass fatalities series using the Census Bureau’s X13 tool (results not presented here for economy of space).

3.C Alternative measures of confidence

In the baseline specification we use fatalities in mass shootings to instrument the expectational component of consumer confidence, namely ICE. Figure 11 shows that results remain robust when we measure consumer confidence by the overall index of consumer sentiment (ICS), which captures both the expectational component (ICE) and sentiment regarding current economic conditions (ICC). Figure 10 shows that results are also robust to using our instrument as a proxy for consumer sentiment regarding business conditions in the country as a whole over the next 12 months (BUS12).⁵ We note that F -statistics remain high, albeit lower than in our baseline

⁵Results are also robust to considering consumer sentiment regarding economic conditions in the next 5 years (BUS5).

Figure 9: Including Month Dummies in the Baseline VAR

specification (see main paper, Table 1).

Figure 10: Alternative Confidence - Proxying BUS12

4 Detrending

In our baseline specification, we apply a fourth-order time polynomial to detrend our instrument and all macro variables in the VAR except for the federal funds rate. In this section, we show that

Figure 11: Alternative Confidence - Proxying ICS

results remain robust when we do not detrend (i) our instrument, and (ii) the macroeconomic variables in the VAR, by a fourth-order time polynomial. Figure 12 shows that impulse responses look unchanged when we do not detrend mass shooting fatalities. Similarly, Figure 13 shows that impulse responses remain robust when we do not detrend the macroeconomic variables in the benchmark VAR.

Figure 12: No Detrending of Mass Fatalities

Figure 13: No Detrending of Macroeconomic Variables

5 Additional Fundamentals

A potential concern is that mass shootings could lead to increases in spending on policing and security, thereby raising future taxation. Table 7 shows the results of Granger causality tests between our identified shocks (or alternatively mass fatalities directly) and the exogenous tax change series of Romer and Romer (2010). Granger causality is not detected in either direction.

Table 7: Granger Causality Wald Test - Tax Shocks, 1965:1-2007:8

Part A: Benchmark VAR				
Equation	Excluded	Chi-squared	lags	Prob > Chi-squared
R&R tax shock	Sentiment shock	22.91	18	0.19
Sentiment shock	R&R tax shock	16.67	18	0.55
R&R tax shock	MassFat ₇	19.4	18	0.37
MassFat ₇	R&R tax shock	6.31	18	1.0

6 Local Projection Responses

In this section, we show that our results are qualitatively robust to the IV method used for estimating the dynamic responses of sentiment shocks. Figure 14 presents impulse responses for labor market variables, consumption, TFP and EPU estimated using local projection methods for our baseline sample period (1965:1-2007:8). The continuous line depicts point estimates of the impact of the identified sentiment shock, while dark grey and light grey areas represent 68 and 90 percent confidence bands, respectively (based on Newey-West estimates of the covariance

matrix). The dynamic responses of vacancies and labor market tightness (first row), consumption of durables and non-durables (second row), and utilization-adjusted TFP and the EPU index (last row), are qualitatively consistent with the Proxy VAR findings.

Figure 14: LP-IV: Consumer Sentiment Shock IRF - Other Variables, 1965-2007m8

7 Forecast Error Variance Decomposition - SVAR

In the main paper, we report the LP-IV statistics for the forecast variance ratio in order to be conservative and because one might have concerns about non-invertibility in the VAR setting,

which would bias the forecast error variance decomposition.⁶ Nonetheless, here we report computed estimates for the FEVD in our Proxy SVAR analysis. As can be seen in Table 8, the results from the SVAR indicate a high contribution of sentiment shocks especially to business cycle variations of consumer sentiments, industrial production, and the unemployment rate. The results are broadly in line with the LP-IV stats (upper bounds).

Table 8: Forecast Error Variance Decomposition - SVAR Estimates

Horizon	ICE	IP	UR	CPI	FFR	U12	S&P
1m	78.6	14.7	21.4	25.3	0.1	13.9	3.1
6m	61.1	28.4	36.1	14.8	11.5	10.6	3.8
12m	51.5	29.8	39.9	12.7	14.5	8.3	5.5
24m	43.6	24.1	36.3	7.7	16.7	5.2	6.5
48m	37.9	19.7	25.5	3.6	14.6	5.3	11.9
60m	29.5	17.0	20.8	3.2	12.1	6.4	12.4

8 Forecast Variance Ratio - Additional Variables

The main paper presents point estimates and 90 percent upper and lower bounds of the identified set of the forecast variance ratio (FVR) statistic for the baseline variables. This section presents FVR statistics for additional variables relating to consumption and the labor market (see Figure 15). For durable goods consumption, the sentiment shock contributes very little below seven months, after which the point estimates of the identified set gradually rise to around 20 percent with the 90 percent upper bound reaching above 30 percent. For nondurables consumption, the point estimates of the identified set of the FVR are similar to those of durable consumption goods spending, reaching slightly higher levels with a slightly longer time lag. For labor market tightness, the FVR upper bound peaks at 30 percent at the seven-month horizon before gradually decreasing and hovering around 20 percent in the longer run (the point estimate peaks at around 20 percent and hovers around 10 percent). For vacancies, the FVR upper bound peaks at over 25 percent at the seven-month horizon before gradually decreasing towards just over 10 percent in the long run (the point estimate of the identified set peaks at 18 percent before gradually reducing to below 5 percent from 20 months onwards). All in all, we find further evidence of important contributions of the sentiment shock to business cycle variations in the real economy, when considering both consumption and labor market indicators.

⁶As shown by Plagborg-Møller and Wolf (2019), without invertibility, the Proxy SVAR estimator would overstate the forecast variance decomposition (FEVD) of the identified shock.

Figure 15: FVR: Consumption and Labor Market Indicators

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